

VISIBLE AND UV LIGHT MEASUREMENT METHODOLOGY

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Abstract: UV and visible light measurements are fundamental in various areas, such as health, agriculture and environmental sciences. These measurements help to evaluate the quality of light that influences biological processes, such as bacteria proliferation, seed germination in scientific environments, and also makes it possible to understand the risks associated with sun exposure. The methodology involves the use of equipment such as photometers and spectrometers, which allow to quantify the intensity of radiation in different wavelengths. The proper calibration of the sensors is crucial to ensure the accuracy of the data collected. In addition, configuration of the measurement environment should be controlled to avoid external interference. With the correct analysis of the data, it is possible to apply the results to practices that promote safety and efficiency in crops and the protection of public health. The objective of this article is to present a methodology of visible and UV light measurements.

Keywords: UV light, light measurement, health sensors, agriculture sensors.

INTRODUCTION

Ultraviolet (UV) and visible (VL) light usage in biological environments is a significant research area due to its applications in diagnosis, treatment and study of biological processes [1].

Light can be used to control and monitor chemical reactions and biological processes with high accuracy and sensitivity [2].

UV and VL measurement usually involves the use of appropriate sensors such as photometers, spectrometers or radiometers, for photometers measurement measuring light intensity in different wavelengths, with UV options and visible light [3].

Spectrometers offer a more detailed analysis of the light spectrum, allowing you to identify and quantify different wavelengths, while radiometer can measure radiation in different spectral bands, including UV [4].

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One Lux is defined as the illuminance that results from the distribution of a luminous flow of a lumen over a square meter area. This measure is fundamental to evaluate the amount of light that focuses on a surface, being used in lighting projects to ensure adequate lighting levels [6],[7].

Lux meter offer a more detailed analysis of the light spectrum, allowing the operator to identify and quantify different wavelengths. Radiometers: Specialized in measuring radiation in different spectral bands, including UV.

Lux meter is an instrument used to measure the density of the light intensity present in a particular location. Its unit of measurement is Lux, and a lux corresponds to one watt per square meter (1 lux = 1 w/m²). This type of equipment is suitable for used in industries, offices, hospitals, homes, schools, restaurants, among other spaces. It basically consists of a photoelectric cell and a milliampere (mA) meter. The photoelectric cell is a semiconductor, light -sensitive material. When light is on the photocell, the semiconductor current formation occurs, which after amplified is measured in the ammeter, using a graduated scale adequately to measure the illuminance level, which

is proportional to the luminous radiation incident at the site [8].

METHOD

In this section we describe the process used for UV measurement. For data collection of this article, the lux meter and radiometer and SP-215 pyranometer sensor used to measure global radiation, or only direct or diffuse, in wavelengths from ultraviolet to infrared electromagnetic spectrum, in Figure 1 we can see the Model used for measurement.

Figure 1 - Instrutherm Lux meter

Before we realize the measurements, it is important to calibrate sensors with standard light sources to ensure accuracy in results so that there is no noise in the measurement. TABLE 1 presents the parametrization values used for that.

TABLE 1 – Parametrization

tempo	lamp vis (ON/OFF)	lamp uv (ON/OFF)	sensor (W/m ²) (louis.s/m ²)	luximetro		radiometro		km.lux	koffset.lu x	LuxLabor	Km.uv	Kl.uv	LuxLabor(mW/m ²)
				valor lux	valor uW/cm ²	valor mW/m ²	valor						
1	1658	ON	ON	73	20000	1340	13400	0,90411	-46,00	20,00	0,10959	5400	13400
2	1700	ON	ON	73	20000	1340	13400	0,90411	-46,00	20,00	0,10959	5400	13400
3	1792	ON	ON	73	20000	1340	13400	0,90411	-46,00	20,00	0,10959	5400	13400
4	1704	ON	ON	73	20000	1340	13400	0,90411	-46,00	20,00	0,10959	5400	13400
5	1792	ON	ON	73	20000	1340	13400	0,90411	-46,00	20,00	0,10959	5400	13400
6	1704	ON	ON	73	20000	1340	13400	0,90411	-46,00	20,00	0,10959	5400	13400
7	1708	ON	ON	73	20000	1340	13400	0,90411	-46,00	20,00	0,10959	5400	13400
8	1710	ON	ON	73	20000	1340	13400	0,90411	-46,00	20,00	0,10959	5400	13400
9	1713	ON	ON	73	20000	1340	13400	0,90411	-46,00	20,00	0,10959	5400	13400
10	1715	ON	ON	73	20000	1340	13400	0,90411	-46,00	20,00	0,10959	5400	13400
11	1717	ON	ON	73	20000	1340	13400	0,90411	-46,00	20,00	0,10959	5400	13400

To minimize external interference, such as light sources, it is essential to choose a space that allows the full control of lighting conditions and implementation of luminous insulation techniques can help create an environment conducive to rigorous measurements [9].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TABLE 2 presents the VL and UV power values measured.

TABLE 2 – Total Power

SYMBOL	LEGEND	VALUE (W/m ²)
P _T	TOTAL RADIATED POWER	73.00
P _{TVL}	VL RADIATED POWER	66.00
P _{TUV}	UV RADIATED POWER	8.00
RESULTING TOTAL		74.00

Following we present the calculation results of TABLE 2.

$$P_T = P_{TVL} + P_{TUV}$$

$$P_{TVL} = P_T$$

$$P_{TUV} = P_T \times VLcoef(\%)$$

$$P_{TVL} (W/m^2) = P_{Med} (klux) \times VLcoef$$

$$Conversion = P_{TVL} (W/m^2) / P_{Med} (klux)$$

$$Conversion = P_T \times VLcoef(\%) / P_{Med}$$

$$Conversion = 3,3$$

Measurements in controlled environments is critical to ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the results obtained, as shown in Table 1 VL Lamp and Lamp UV are on and off. Tests were performed and a simple mathematical calculation was used to solve the equation and harmonize what was requested.

CONCLUSIONS

This article has taken as application methodology studies and tests done in the laboratory to facilitate and combine UV and VL values in the same application. Today the market offers only equipment to perform these assessments, using the method we can apply UV and VL values in the same segment. In future projects, they can be performed with the objective to increase the accuracy of the final results, using existing sensors in the market, it is intended to evaluate the course of a cloud application so that the data can be analyzed in real time, used logic and advanced language programming to improve the result.

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